

A STUDY ON THE INFLUENCE OF COLORS ON THE CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOUR

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Abstract:

Color plays an important role in marketing products. It is a powerful marketing tool that influences consumer purchases in many aspects. Marketers must explore the harmony of colors for successful marketing of products. Nearly all products sold today have colorful facades. Selecting the right colors to use has an enormous impact on product sales. While no single set of rules governs color choices, research has established general guidelines based on the principle of associative learning, the relationship between color and emotion. The conclusion is that color has a major role towards the choice of the product purchased by the respondents were the companies has to look after the satisfaction level and availability of colors towards their brand which leads to increase in profitability and turnover for the companies in future period of time.

Key Words: Colors, Behaviour & Marketing

Introduction:

Marketing is an important stage on the modernized production and distribution. It has a special significance in the modern management of business and industry. It is one of the important management concepts, unless it is properly understood and put into practice in the right use. Many of the business or industrial enterprise will collapse or prove failure. Marketing is so basic that it is not enough to have strong sales department and entrust marketing to it:

- The business decision must be consumer oriented.
- Marketing must increase profit.
- Marketing must be dynamic in process.

The major purpose of marketing is to satisfy human needs by delivering products of various types of buyers when and where they want them and at a reasonable price. Product available at right time will make customer satisfied. Customer satisfaction is a person's feelings of pleasure or disappointment resulting from comparing a product's perceived performance he expects of it. Complete customer satisfaction is achieved by understanding customer requirements and delivering superior quality goods and services.

The modern marketer is called upon to set the marketing objectives, develop the marketing plan, organize the marketing function, implement the marketing plan or programme (marketing mix) and control the marketing programme to ensure the accomplishment of the set marketing objectives. The marketing programme covers producer planning or merchandising, price, promotion and distribution.

Color plays a major role in marketing products. It has a major influencing effect on consumer buying behaviour. It is a powerful marketing tool that significantly influences consumer purchases, so much so that it accounts for 85% of the reason why someone decides to purchase a product (Hemphill, 1996). Marketers must understand the psychology of color in order to use it effectively. Psychology of color is the study of hues as a determinant of human behaviour. Color influences perceptions that are not obvious, such as the taste of food. Colors can also enhance the effectiveness of placebos. For example, red or orange pills are generally used as stimulants. Color can indeed influence a person; however, it is important to remember that these effects differ between people. Factors such as gender, age, and culture can influence how an individual perceives color. For instance, heterosexual men tend to report that red outfits enhance female attractiveness, while heterosexual females deny any outfit color impacting that of men.

Review of Literature:

Color has three basic properties: Hue, Lightness, and Chroma (Fairchild, 2013). Variation in any or all of these properties could influence downstream effect, cognition, or behaviour, yet only hue is considered in most theorising (most likely because experientially, it is the most salient color property). Lightness and Chroma also undoubtedly have implications for psychological functioning (e.g., lightness: Kareklas et al., 2014; Chroma: Lee et al., 2013); lightness has received some attention within conceptual metaphor theory (Meier, in press; see also Prado León and Rosales-Cinco, 2011), but Chroma has been almost entirely overlooked, as has

the issue of combinations of hue, lightness, and chroma. It has been proved that colors have a strong effect on perception and therefore colors of packaging can be important. The right choice of colors is an important factor in creating the impression needed to influence brand and product selection (Gofman 2010). Color of packaging has an important role in helping the customers make apart one company product from the other. Cheskin (1957) says that the selection of colors and color combinations is a necessary process for creating a good design package. Color is a key element of design due to the fact that it is usually vivid and memorable. The package color can have a significant effect on consumers' ability to recognise a product.

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Statement of the Problem:

The first in research is formulating a research problem. It is the important stage in applied research, as poorly defined problems will not yield useful result. It is rightly said, "a problem well defined is half-solved". Poorly defined problems cause confusion and do not allow the research to develop a good research design. The problem identified for the study is to find out the attitude and perception of the consumers towards purchasing based on colors.

Objectives of the Study:

- To determine Consumers' perception towards Colors
- To understand consumer buying behaviour of consumers based on colors.
- To determine the satisfaction level of customers towards colors with various brands.

Scope of the Study:

- The scope of the project is to know the consumers' perception towards Colors in recent trends.
- The study will help the company to understand the behaviour of individual while purchasing based on Colors.
- The study will help the company to make strategies to improve their services to meet customers' expectation.
- The study will help the company to know the expectation of company.

Research Methodology: Research methodology is the description, explanation and justification of various methods of conducting research. This area deals with the research design, sources of data collection, sampling design, size of the sample, hypothesis, and statistical tools used for the data analysis and interpretation.

Research Design: The study is descriptive in nature. Descriptive study is taken up when the researcher is interested in knowing the present status regarding the particular area of interest. The conclusion are arrived from the collected data. Statistical tools are to be used for the analysis of collected data from the survey. As through a detailed study only the objectives can be achieved. By this the result can be achieved easily and detailed form

Geographical Area: The area at which the study conducted was with Coimbatore district.

Sample Size: The number of samples collected for the study is 120 consumers.

Sources of Data:

Primary Data: Primary data are those data which are collected for the first time which is original in character. Here primary data are collected from consumers through a well structured questionnaire.

Secondary Data

The secondary data will be collected from company websites, industry profile, manuals, journals etc.

Statistical Techniques Used for Analysis: Simple Percentage analysis and Chi Square Test

Limitations of the Study:

- The study was limited to a particular areas of Coimbatore district, therefore the findings and conclusions are valid only for these areas.

- The collection of data find some difficult, due to lack of co-operation from some respondents.
- Since the research study has to be completed within a specified period, a small segment of the customers has been taken.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Personal Factors	Particulars	Frequency	Percent
Age	Upto 20	36	30
	21-30	36	30
	31-40	24	20
	40 and above	24	20
	Total	120	100
Gender	Male	2	1.7
	Female	118	98.3
	Total	120	100
Income level	10,000-20,000	72	60
	21,000-30,000	32	26.7
	31,000-40,000	4	3.3
	50,000 and above	12	10
	Total	120	100

Interpretation

The above table shows about the age of the respondents were out of 120 respondents 30% are from the age group of up to 20 and 21-30, 20% are from the age group of 31-40 and 40 and above. 1.7% are male and 98.3% are female. 60% are earning between 10000-20000, 26.7% are earning between 21000-30000, 3.3% are earning between 31000-40000 and 10% are earning above 50000.

Knowledge about Colors with Various Brand:

	Frequency	Percent
Advertisement	56	46.7
Own family	36	30
T. V	12	10
Newspaper	16	13.3
Total	120	100

Interpretation:

The above table show about knowledge of the respondents about colors with various brand were out of 120 respondents 46.7% came to know about the colors of the brand through advertisement, 30% know through their own family, 10% know through TV and 13.3% know through news paper.

Factors Influencing to Choose the Brand Based on Color:

	Frequency	Percent
Price	12	10
Quality	60	50
Taste	32	26.7
Availability	12	10
Packaging	4	3.3
Total	120	100

Interpretation:

The above table show about factors influencing to choose the brand were out of 120 respondents 10% said as price, 50% said as quality, 26.7% said as taste, 10% said as availability and 3.3% said as packaging.

Satisfaction towards the Quality of Colors:

	Frequency	Percent
Highly Satisfied	12	10
Satisfied	52	43.3
Neutral	36	30
Dissatisfied	12	10
Highly dissatisfied	8	6.7
Total	120	100

Interpretation:

The above table show about satisfaction towards the quality of Colors by the respondents were out of 120 respondents 10% are highly satisfied, 43.3% are satisfied, 30% are neutral, 10% are dissatisfied and 6.7% are highly dissatisfied.

Respondents Finding Easy to Buy the Product Because of Its Availability of Colors towards the Brand:

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Agree	12	10
Agree	48	40
Neutral	48	40
Disagree	8	6.7
Strongly Disagree	4	3.3
Total	120	100

Interpretation:

The above table show about respondents finding easy to buy the product because of its availability colors towards the brand were out of 120 respondents 10% strongly agree, 40% agree, 40% are neutral, 6.7% disagree and 3.3% strongly disagree.

Respondents Having Idea for Changing the Brand Based on Color Availability:

	Frequency	Percent
Yes	28	23.3
No	92	76.7
Total	120	100

Interpretation:

The above table show about respondents having idea for changing the brand based on color availability were out of 120 respondents 23.3% said that they have idea of changing the brand and 76.7% said that they don't have idea of changing the brand.

Age * Satisfaction towards the Quality of Colors:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between age and satisfaction towards the quality of Colors

Crosstab							
Count							
		Satisfaction towards the quality of Colors					Total
		Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Neutral	Dissatisfied	Highly dissatisfied	
Age	Upto 20	8	8	12	8	0	36
	21-30	4	16	8	0	8	36
	31-40	0	16	8	0	0	24
	40 and above	0	12	8	4	0	24
Total		12	52	36	12	8	120

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	49.345 ^a	12	0.032
Likelihood Ratio	58.188	12	0
Linear-by-Linear Association	0.017	1	0.897
N of Valid Cases	120		

a. 12 cells (60.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.60.

Interpretation: The above table shows about the comparison between age and satisfaction towards the quality of Colors were the level of significance is at 0.032 which is lesser than 0.05. Hence alternative hypothesis H₁ is accepted. It shows that there is a significant relationship between age and satisfaction towards the quality of Colors. Maximum of the respondents are satisfied towards quality of Colors and they are from the age group of 21-40.

Findings:

- Maximum of the respondents are from the age group up to 20 and 21-30.
- Most of the respondents are female in our survey.
- Maximum of the respondents are earning between 10000-20000.
- Maximum of the respondents are satisfied towards quality of Colors.
- Most of the respondents agree and they don't have awareness towards finding easy to buy the product because of its availability of colors.

Suggestions:

- It is important to recognize that color trends are not permanent, and can fluctuate over a period of time. Therefore, it is important to stay up to date with current marketing research on color in order to make the best decisions for a company.

- In both reviewing advances in and identifying weaknesses of the literature on color and psychological functioning, it is important to bear in mind that the existing theoretical and empirical work is at the nascent stage of development.

Conclusion:

The conclusion is that color has a major role towards the choice of the product purchased by the respondents were the companies has to look after the satisfaction level and availability of colors towards their brand which leads to increase in profitability and turnover for the companies in future period of time.

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